

What is the cultural value of brand museums? A case study on Philips Museum

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Introduction

In November 2022, Hermes did an exhibition at Mumbai IBFF ('Hermès Heritage - In Motion | Hermès USA', n.d.). This was the third installation of a four-part series travelling exhibition by Hermes to showcase their exquisite craftsmanship and various products over the years ('Harnessing the Heritage of 185 Years of Hermès In Motion', n.d.; 'THE EXHIBITION | Hermès UAE', n.d.). Shortly after Mahindra Group opened its museum in Mumbai ('The Mahindra Group's New Museum Is a Tribute to an Enduring Legacy | Architectural Digest India', n.d.). Godrej Archives and Tata Central Archives were already set up a decade before. This a new transformation that is slowly happening with businesses in India. Heritage Management companies like Eka Resources ('Eka Resources - Cultural Research, Archiving & Outreach', n.d.) and Past Perfect ('Past Perfect | Heritage Management Company', n.d.) have been set up to provide archival services to such companies. They have set up archives for various brands have set up museums and did temporary exhibitions across the country. However, this 'museumification' or 'artification' (Shapiro 2019) is not limited to India, in fact, India is just now catching up to this global trend of corporate archives and brand museums.

As our society descends into late capitalism, attention becomes a new economy (Bueno 2016). The attention of the consumer is drawn through a range of spectacles i.e. retail spectacles (Hollenbeck et al., 2008). Derived from Hollenbeck et al.'s (2008) categorization of retail spectacles, brands utilize three distinct types of environments to facilitate consumption at varying levels as specified in the table below [Figure 1].

Figure 1: Table of Different Retail Experience, derived from the text of Hollenbeck et al. (2008) on Retail Spectacles

As most shopping turns online, traditional brick-and-mortar stores offer experiences that encapsulate consumers' attention and interest to strengthen the consumer-brand bond. Many brands have started opening themed flagship stores that offer a unique and immersive experience of the brand with a string focus on consumption and zero focus on history. For instance LEGO store in London ('De Flagship Store in Londen Leicester Square - Help Onderwerpen - Klantenservice - LEGO.Com NL', n.d.), Uniqlo Store in Tokyo ('UNIQLO Flagship Shop "UNIQLO TOKYO" Has Opened up in the Classy Town of Ginza', n.d.), and Nike in New York ('Nike House of Innovation NYC. New York, NY. Nike.Com', n.d.).

With an increasing number of options for consumers to choose from, brands are attempting to maintain loyalty and strengthen connections in an exposed factory or lab model by opening experience centres. These centres can also share some early beginnings of the brand to showcase the authentic process, allowing for consumer appreciation. There is a strong focus on history, but the end goal is entertainment, for instance, Heineken Experience Centre in Amsterdam, Guinness Storehouse in Dublin, and World of Coca-Cola Atlanta.

The brand museums take this one step further; they have a traditional museum-like setting where the brand is positioned in a historical and educational context (Hollenbeck et al., 2008). Brand Museums use heritage tools and technology to create spaces for different kinds of consumption of their objects (Chaney et al., 2018). In the museumification process, the brand gets transformed into an idealistic version of itself where the value of the object is not attached to its use but to its potential to be an artifact (Di Giovine 2008). It plays on the long legacy of the brand in the lives of the consumer.

Major players in industries like FMCG (fast-moving consumer goods), automobiles, furniture, household appliances, and fashion have all followed this trajectory of the retail showroom to themed flagship store to experience centres and now museums. For example, Omega Museum in Switzerland, Nestle in Switzerland, Philips Museum in Eindhoven, Musee Yves Saint Laurent in Paris, HMT Watch Museum in Bangalore and many more. There's a thin line between experience centres and brand museums. A brand can use museum technologies to tell the story of the company educationally and historically and nudge you towards consuming the product as part of the experience. We often see this phenomenon in the case of FMCG brands like Coca-Cola or Laughing Cow (Hollenbeck et al., 2008).

According to the International Council of Museums, the museum is “a not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society that researches, collects, conserves, interprets and exhibits tangible and intangible heritage. Open to the public, accessible and inclusive, museums foster diversity and sustainability. They operate and communicate ethically, professionally and with the participation of communities, offering varied experiences for education, enjoyment, reflection and knowledge sharing” (ICOM 2022). Brand Museums use the same idea to tell the story of the corporation. We see this trend with long-standing corporations and companies that have been around for longer than five decades and often over a century. An old company or corporation has a brand value that transcends generations. Consumers buy their products not for performance but for their brand (Pulh et al., 2019). According to Pulh (2019, 2197), “through brand museums, companies give more than what the consumer is accustomed to receiving in a conventional commercial. By staging its heritage, the brand makes its history, know-how, and symbols accessible to consumers in a transmission logic whose message is *“this is your heritage”*”. As an increasing number of companies opt for the heritage route for their brands, it is becoming crucial to determine whether they are attempting to change the consumption pattern of the same brand or if they are bringing something valuable to the community. These brand museums also actively align themselves with the mainstream philosophy of providing immersive experiences to attract a new kind of consumer base.

Noticing these trends, the paper will attempt to investigate the cultural value brand museums have in the field of heritage and how they contribute to the larger discourse of culture and heritage. In the meticulous selection of the right museum brand, a thorough examination of various categories was undertaken. The selected museum had to be a widely recognized brand

globally, with a significant contribution to the development of the region. This criterion aimed to identify museums that, beyond showcasing the brand story, played a crucial role in cultural narratives. Numerous museums and brand-related establishments in the Netherlands were considered, including the Heineken Experience Centre, the UNESCO World Heritage site of the Van Nelle Factory, and the first Albert Heijn departmental stores. While most of these brands contributed significantly to the local communities and major impact on the micro level, many of these lacked certain essential factors. For instance, the Van Nelle factory, while no longer a brand, retained architectural significance, contrasting Albert Heijn which was preserved as first ever store, rather than a museum, and Heineken functioned as both an experience centre and museum. Philips Museum Eindhoven has been chosen for this analysis because of its long-standing relationship with the city of its origin, Eindhoven, and the global impact that the brand has had over the last century. The museum is situated in the same place where the first factory was built in Eindhoven.

This paper will utilize the exhibition analysis tool developed by the Reinwardt Academy to evaluate the cultural value of the brand in the larger discourse of the heritage field. First, it will provide an overview of the research method. Next, the paper will discuss the findings and the result of the method employed. Finally, it will compare the findings with relevant literature in the field and conclude the research question.

Methodology

This paper deploys the exhibition analysis tools provided during the Researching Concept module. Both the Handout Exhibition Analysis – curator perspective shared on 25th September 2023 and the Handout Exhibition Analysis – visitor perspective shared on 3rd October 2023 has been used for this research. For the duration of this study, this method was selected to evaluate the intent and message of the museum exhibit. The research unfolded in two phases: initial visits as a visitor to capture raw first impressions, followed by subsequent visits as a curator to analyse exhibition structures, technologies deployed, and thematic breakdowns. This comprehensive approach gave a holistic understanding of the museum's storytelling methods and cultural impact.

The author's first visit (14/01/2024) to the museum was as a visitor, following exploration of the museum's website and social media, and having previously visited other brand museums. The second visit (19/01/2024) as a curator was conducted a week after the first visit, with the intent of understanding the structure of the narrative through the details of text labels along with a self-guided audio tour. Along with following the exhibition analysis handout, audio and written notes were taken during both visits.

The museum tour was also supplemented with an outdoor tour of the city through the Philips Campus Tour Connect app [Figure 2] that provided a 15 km cycling/ walking self-initiated tour across from the north to the south of the city of Eindhoven. The tour takes you through Philip's impressive industrial heritage. At each venue, you'll receive information, participate in quizzes, and enjoy pitstops for lunch or coffee ('Philips Campus Connect Tour | Philips Museum', n.d.) This tour will not be considered in the exhibition analysis. However, its purpose will be taken into account in the results.

While it would have been a logical progression to conduct visitor studies in order to effectively gauge the impact on its audience, this particular step is currently beyond the scope of the paper and may be subject to exploration in future research.

Figure 2: The Screenshots from the app of 'Philips Campus Connect Tour'

Results

Exhibition Analysis – Visitor Perspective

(1) Social

	Excellent	Good	Not quite	Poor
“Entertainment”				
1. Is the exhibition an enjoyable place to spend time with family and/or friends?	✓			
2. Is access and orientation well taken care off?		✓		
3. Does the museum offer good facilities and services?		✓		
4. Is museum staff welcoming to all?		✓		
5. Does the museum exhibits stimulate social interaction?			✓	

Figure 3: Handout Exhibition Analysis - Visitor Perspective, Pg 1

Analysis: While the exhibits had an entertaining element, the focus was more on imparting knowledge and information about different aspects of the products. It is worth noting that all the staff members working in the museum were middle-aged and older. The staff did not interact proactively, though answered questions whenever approached by a visitor.

(2) Intellectual

	Excellent	Good	Not quite	Poor
“Knowledge”				
1. Does the exhibition encourage your interest and knowledge?		✓		
2. Is the exhibition well structured?	✓			
3. Are the exhibition texts well written and easy to understand?	✓			
4. Does the exhibition provide sufficient background information on the subject?		✓		
5. Does the exhibition offer multiple perspectives on the subject?			✓	

Figure 4: Handout Exhibition Analysis - Visitor Perspective, Pg 2

Analysis: It is evident that the museum is a story of Philips by Philips. The exhibition and museum attempted to encapsulate the stories of Philips by touching upon its prominent innovations and contributions to society. The permanent exhibit had a very clear one-directional message of Philips’ contribution to the local community and the region of Eindhoven. While the museum evidently depicts the impact Philips has had on the region’s development. As mentioned in Figure 4 for point five, the exhibits do not offer multiple perspectives of the larger Philips story. One could see in the film about Philips TV, where in the year 1950 the organization had to deal with some form of operational resistance from the government and such stories of hurdles have not been covered in the museum.

(3) Emotional

	Excellent	Good	Not quite	Poor
<i>"Experience"</i>				
1. Does the exhibition speak to all the senses?			✓	
2. Does the exhibition offer an immersive experience?		✓		
3. Does the exhibition include touching (personal) stories or objects?			✓	
4. Does the exhibition include aesthetic appealing objects?		✓		
5. Does the exhibition make you feel connected to people of the past and/or other places?	✓			

Figure 5: Handout Exhibition Analysis - Visitor Perspective, Pg 3

Analysis: The exhibition offers several immersive experiences through sound, video, model sets and touch and interactive digital elements. However, it lacked tactile and smell. With all the various appliances and old gadgets present, one could consider building a case to incorporate a few objects from the display into the exhibition narrative through guided play. While Philips showcases the community-building initiatives undertaken by it in Eindhoven, those moments are few and spread out. In one of the showcases, one could observe that many of Philips’ first employees were women, though this wasn't captured anywhere else as dedicated stories or relatable content for the current generation and about women empowerment. When products are presented in a narrative that includes stories of humans, a strong emotional connection with the past is established. It emphasises the community elements associated with Philips.

(4) Spiritual

	Excellent	Good	Not quite	Poor
<i>"Enrichment"</i>				
1. Does the exhibition provide for quiet contemplation (escapism)?				✓
2. Does the exhibition speak to your imagination?				✓
3. Does the exhibition strengthen your (cultural) identity?			✓	
4. Does the exhibition offer food for thought?		✓		
5. Does the exhibition articulate a call to action?				✓

Figure 6: Handout Exhibition Analysis - Visitor Perspective, Pg 4

Analysis: The overarching theme of the museum is identified as encompassing not only the brand but also innovation, community development, design, and scientific discovery. The initial impression that Brand Museum such as Philip merely boasts about themselves dissipates. While the museum rarely offers a space for contemplation, it does instil a sense of pride and understanding regarding the brands' contributions to the development of the world, country, or city, leaving a lasting impression on visitors.

Exhibition Analysis – Curator Perspective

Exhibition analysis sheet

It is recommended to first go through the entire exhibition to get a general impression. During the second tour, when you look closely, you can fill out the exhibition analysis.

Content	Answers and comments
<p>1. State the main theme. Please indicate whether there are any subthemes and if so, which ones?</p>	<p>Philip's history and it's various products. There are subthemes of different category of products such as medicine, light, music</p>
<p>2. What is the core idea? Does the exhibition have a particular message, and if so, which one? Is the message conveyed clearly or are there other, perhaps, better ways?</p>	<p>Philip's contribution to the community and the world at large. The message is conveyed clearly through different chapters and themes, slowly progressing in time.</p>
<p>3. Is the exhibition object-oriented or narrative-oriented? Is it about the objects or are the objects used to tell a story?</p>	<p>Exhibition is narrative oriented. Objects are used to explain the narratives. However, in a few places, the story is about the object itself for examples how the philips light bulb was made. Here the focus is on the object and it's technology.</p>
<p>4. Does the exhibition have a clear spatial layout? Does the layout of the exhibition support the content?</p>	<p>The exhibition starts with a clear spatial layout. After the first 2 chapters, then it opens into a large room, where the next few chapters flow into each other.</p>
Target group	Answers and comments
<p>5. Was the exhibition made for a specific target group, and if so, which one?</p>	<p>Exhibitions caters to all age groups.</p>
<p>6. How did they try to connect to the target group? For instance, by the choice of objects, the angle of the texts, the atmosphere of the exhibition?</p>	<p>For adults, there are many ways to connect. The objects are from everyday life for example home appliances or music players. Philips lighting solutions which are very famous. Documentary films capturing the older audience about the linkages between WWII and Philips. I noticed only one object display for kids that was the CT Scanner with dummy animals.</p>
Communicative tools	Answers and comments
<p>7. Are there any gallery texts, object texts, etc.? What is the order and layering of the texts?</p>	<p>There are both gallery and objects texts. There's an introductory text for each chapter. Then several general text explaining the theme of chapter and a few object text with the description.</p>
<p>8. How is the language used? Informative, visual, businesslike, narrative, popular?</p>	<p>Dual language text for each text panel or label. Dutch has larger font size, while english is smaller. The style is informative and had a narrative tone.</p>
<p>9. What other means of communication are used? AV media, interactives, do-things, models, style rooms, scent, re-enactment? What does each type of medium contribute to the storyline?</p>	<p>There are audio guides, cinema room, several touch screens to view a story in a book form, an interactive map of Eindhoven, audio pieces and at the end an immersive digital space introducing current research and innovation. The contribution of each A/V or interactive element is to provide a deeper connect to the story of Philips</p>
<p>10. In what ways does the exhibition design support the storyline? E.g. colour, type of furniture, use of images, hierarchy of objects.</p>	<p>The colours in the beginning of the exhibition are white and blue highlighting the Philips origin story. We then enter an open layout, which different colors used for different chapters. The open layout suggests parallel developments as opposed to the first 2 chapters which showcased a chronological development.</p>

Figure 7: Handout Exhibition Analysis - Curator Perspective, Reflection Questionnaire

Figure 8: Two visitors watching the film demonstration of 'bulb making' in the Philips Museum, in the chapter 2 section of the exhibition 'the first factory'

Analysis: the entry into the museum follows that of a traditional museum, where there is a ticket counter, museum shop and a cloakroom with lockers and restrooms. In the examination of the exhibition, the narrative structure comes across as a combination of both thematic and chronological approaches. The exhibition is structured around 13 chapters, along with a closing section and two temporary exhibitions. The themes explored in the exhibition include the introduction of Philips as a brand, transitioning from

Figure 10: Street view of the hallway, Philips Museum

Figure 9: View from the street, Philips Museum, housed in the old factory.

Figure 9: Hallway to enter the exhibition space from the ticket counter. The hallway has Philips timeline on the left and a glass wall on the right. The timeline can be viewed from the street

darkness to light, and larger topics such as future building and transformative changes in electricity and medical fields. The exhibition follows a chronological structure that corresponds with the developments in the brand's history.

The hallway leading to the exhibits is adorned with a comprehensive timeline of Philips which is easily visible from the street outside, enticing passersby to visit the museum. The timeline is a compressed version of the exhibit inside and provides an overarching development/progress of Philips company. This hallway serves as a warm-up towards the museum.

The first chapter, 'The Age of Invention' leads to a dark room with an impression of an oil lamp-lit environment

and a replica of Van Gogh's Potato Eaters. The theme of this room is black, and it introduces the first important products and inventions by Philips like the filament bulb tubes for radio, x-ray and television.

Figure 11: Interior view of the Museum

The rooms lead to a blue passage with the model of the first factory i.e. the second chapter. The walls mention all the firsts of Philip. First men who laid the foundation stones for the company, the first employers and the first factory. Since the location of the museum of the old factory itself, one corner of the factory was preserved as is with the old equipment and apparatus for making the bulbs. A video runs overhead on the ceiling to demonstrate the making of the first light bulb.

The next section opens in a big room where the next few chapters flow into each other without a clear sense of direction giving an impression of parallel inventions. [Figure 12] For instance, one can easily go from the third to the seventh. The chapters on the ground floor are (in order), 'lighting up the world', 'outdoor lighting', 'connecting the world', 'cinema', 'making the invisible visible', 'conquering the world', 'the world of research', and 'the rise of Eindhoven'. These eight chapters on the ground floor are divided thematically. The green box in Figure 12 is a temporary exhibit. These chapters are

seemingly divided into different departments of Philips such as lighting, radio, TV, medical and research. The theme is loosely tied in as chapter 6 – cinema, chapter 8 – conquering the world and chapter 10 – the rise of Eindhoven does not fit into the departments. But rather offer an overview of the Philips' work. There are several types of text labels, thematic text gives a brief introduction to the chapter, followed a several descriptive texts providing context to the objects, situating them within the timeline and mentioning notable figures in the history of Philips. Finally, the object labels provide the title and date of the objects. The descriptive text takes precedence across the exhibition.

The cinema section focuses on the impact of Philips during World War II and the subsequent era of television in the 1950s. The tenth chapter sheds light on Philips' influence on Eindhoven, emphasizing the contribution it made to the city's development.

On your way to the next floor, the eleventh room is a conference, which usually holds workshops for younger audiences or talks /events. The top floor of the exhibition has chapters 12 and 13, living with Technology and Philips and the music

Figure 12: Layout of the open floor plan of the Philips Museum, chapter 3 to 10

industry(respectively). As the titles suggest, these two chapters focus on Philips and popular culture. With the life-size living room model set, a row of everyday electrical appliances in vitrines is punctuated by music labels by Philips. Between these two is another temporary exhibition on Philips Graphic Art from 1910-1950s, very thoughtfully placed as it brings the popular imagination to life of these appliances. The final section of the museum is a window into the future with Philips on their current research and work with interactive projections. The exit staircase from the museum leads to the museum café and another temporary exhibit on the football club of Philips. Since sports was considered a recreational activity, its placement adjacent to a café implies a relaxed consumption of this content.

This tour was supplemented with a guided audio tour (available in 4 languages i.e. Dutch, English, German, and French) There were audio spots for both permanent and temporary exhibits. The audio tour provided context and story behind the objects with a few anecdotes. The tone of the narrative is direct, formal and in third person both in audio and text. The overarching voice across the exhibition is predominately Philips and it is reflected even in the voice of former employees in chapter 6 – cinema.

Figure 13: Visitors in the Philips Museum interacting with the projection screens.

Figure 14: Visitors in the Philips Museum interacting with the displayed object

Figure 15: Interactive Map in the Philips Museum

Figure 16: Living room model set showcasing various Philips products from the 1960s in the Philips Museum

Discussions and Conclusions

Philips and Eindhoven

The exhibition analysis reinforces Chaney's et al. (2018) outcomes that brand museums endorse two roles: a community representative role and an intergenerational memory role [Figure 17]. A brand museum is an extension of a complex retail environment (Hollenbeck et al., 2008). In placing their brand in an ICOM-defined museum setting, they move away from a purely commercial experience and assert their identity as a heritage artefact (Chaney et al., 2018), thereby pushing the confines of the business and bringing it into the realm of heritage and culture.

Figure 17: the intergenerational and community representation role of the brand in the brand museum. (Chaney et al., 2018, 456)

In the role of a community representation, the Philips Museum’s deep integration in its founding city Eindhoven makes the brand synonymous with an industry that is built with the community. A museum steward at Philips proudly explained when asked, “Philips is Eindhoven and Eindhoven is Philips.” As one exits the Eindhoven Central station, it is easy to spot a logo of Eindhoven written inside a bulb depicting the long-standing relationship between the city and the company.

Figure 18: Engraving of the Eindhoven logo in the ground outside Eindhoven Central station

Interestingly, in a conversation with Vera on 19th January 2023 (attained level 2 in Dutch sign Language from the University of Leiden), she mentioned the gesture for Eindhoven is a bulb i.e. the raising of the arm and turning of the wrist to imitate the turning of a lightbulb (Vera Hoijtingh, in conversation with author, 19 January 2023). This profound cultural integration goes beyond just the signs and the language. Philips spearheaded the city’s growth by building housing, hospitals, recreational centres, and vocational centres. From the audio guide of the museum, one encounters various facts. Firstly, amidst all the industrial development, Philips formed a football team that later became a football club (PSV) running under Philips’ management. Secondly, Louis Kalff, the lead designer of Philips, has its section in the museum exhibit, was

partly responsible for the setting up of the Design Academy in Eindhoven. Philips' influence on the city's design and structure cannot go unnoticed. The history of the city is intricately linked with the history of the company; to remove one would be equivalent to erasing both.

Continuing with the legacy of Philips, its intergenerational memory role comes across clearly. Their history dates back over a century with early beginnings in 1891. It maintained Eindhoven as an operational hub as the company extended its business to countries near and far such as Russia, China and India. It went through the World War II turmoil. The stories of Philips' successes and challenges turn into folklore as former employees share their stories of hardships and eventual wins in short documentary films in chapter 6 of the exhibit. This transformation gives Philips history a sense of timelessness while remaining at the forefront of innovation. The location becomes an active site of heritage itself wherein "the use of the historic site of production and the display of original objects expose the physical traces related to the production activity" (Chaney et al., 2018). For instance, the Van Nelle factory tour in Rotterdam highlights the intertwining of corporate history and architecture. Frequent visits from former employees to relive their past or share their history with grandchildren create an intriguing dynamic in the relationship between past employees and the corporate narrative (Andel 2024). The Philips campus tour app adds to this allure as it extends beyond the walls of the museum and into the city, giving you glimpses of the old community.

Brand Museums and Corporate Archives as a global phenomenon

The worldwide phenomenon of 'museumification' observed in corporations and organizations reflects an extension of the trend evident in the heritage sector. Lowenthal's (1998) concept of the heritage crusade reflects a contemporary trend towards preservation driven by various factors such as the impermanence of objects, societal migration, technological advancements, and a pervasive sense of nostalgia. These waves of urgency to safeguard cultural artefacts stem from a collective fear of loss and forgetfulness (Lowenthal 1998). Goulding (2000) also notes the phenomenon of the commodification of the past to create authenticity for mass-produced goods (Goulding 2000). Similarly, corporations and businesses are actively engaged in collecting and preserving their historical artefacts and memories. As Andrew Hull observes, these collections hold intrinsic value as they document the economic, labour, trade, innovation, and craft aspects of modern society. By promoting their collections and fostering collaborative engagement, corporate archives have the potential to construct alternative narratives that offer insights into various facets of social and economic history (Hull and Scott 2020). For instance, the case of the Godrej typewriter book highlights the significance of product design and cultural growth (Bhatia and Chaudhuri 2016) while museums like the Museum of Brands in London provide a window into the consumer culture and lifestyles of past generations ('What to Expect – Museum of Brands', n.d.).

However, the Throwaway Project initiated by the House of European History brings to light the potential pitfalls of excessive collecting, as some objects lose their perceived importance over time. The proliferation of the "memory boom" in recent decades has resulted in the establishment of numerous archives and museums dedicated to preserving diverse aspects of the cultural heritage (Parliament et al. 2022). These institutions, as Sterling notes, are departing from traditional models to become dynamic centres of historical exploration and heritage interpretation. Examples such as the Museum of Broken Relationships, Museum of Capitalism, and Museum of Non-Humanity exemplify the evolving role and definition of museums,

challenging conventional notions and expanding the scope of cultural representation (Sterling 2020).

Brand-consumer relation in a heritage environment

To grasp the cultural significance of the brand museum, it is essential to understand the role heritage environments play in shaping brand-consumer relations. Hollenbeck et al. (2008) identify brand museums as a distinct category within themed retail environments, emphasizing their role in educating consumers about a brand's history and cultural meaning. In the Middle Ages, retail spaces like blacksmiths' shops allowed customers to witness production first-hand, fostering a sense of transparency and connection to the craft. However, in the late 19th century, production became less visible to consumers. In the late 20th century, there was a resurgence in exposing shoppers to the production process, enhancing the perceived value of the brand by creating a sense of intimacy with craftsmanship (Hollenbeck et al., 2008). This trend aligns with broader shifts in economies, moving from industrial to service-based models, and now emphasizing the experience economy, where unique and engaging experiences hold increasing value (Pine and Gilmore 1999). Retail experiences are no longer solely about purchasing products; they aim to evoke feelings of fantasy and enjoyment (Pine and Gilmore 1999). Research suggests that brands can generate economic benefits by creating non-economic environments that add value to local communities, thereby enhancing customer-brand relationships and fostering brand loyalty (Riviezzo et al. 2022). Many archiving services across the world (such as Centre for Business History in Stockholm) use this approach of 'history marketing', where a company's authentic story is leveraged as a strategic asset to build its brand and enhance credibility ('History as a Strategic Asset', n.d.). However, Nissley and Cassey (2022) contend that corporate museum organizations strategically curate memories, positioning them as strategic assets for brands. This organizational memory is not neutral, as memories are subjective, and exhibitions are not merely passive artefacts (Nissley and Casey 2002). As demonstrated in exhibition analyses, brand museums actively promote a singular narrative of development and success, aligning with strategic brand objectives. This highlights the deliberate construction of memory and narrative within these spaces, shaping visitor perceptions and reinforcing brand identities.

Conclusion

Despite effectively engaging audiences through interactive and digital elements, the museum's inclusivity aspect remains deficient. Specifically, it neglects to address alternative narratives, such as the role of women in Philips or various operational challenges and fails to amplify employee stories adequately.

The confirmation of the research question by extant literature suggests that the study has made strides in the right direction. While it reinforces the existing literature, it does not offer definitive insights. As we explore the academic literature on brand museums, there's a predominance of literature in the journals of marketing and management, with minimal representation in heritage journals. It invites further exploration into their cultural value and role, encouraging an interdisciplinary approach that bridges marketing, management, and heritage studies.

However, asserting that brand museums inherently carry cultural value assumes a neutrality that contradicts the inherently politicized nature of museums as institutional entities. Museums are

deeply entrenched in socio-political contexts and are often sites of contestation and negotiation over cultural narratives and power dynamics. Therefore, interpreting brand museums as neutral spaces overlooks their complex roles within broader societal frameworks. As such, a critical examination of the cultural value attributed to brand museums necessitates an acknowledgement of their inherent politicization and the multifaceted dynamics that shape their significance within cultural discourse.

The method of exhibition analysis employed in this study presents certain limitations. Primarily, it reflects the singular perspective of the author, with experience only as an art curator and archivist, having familiarity with heritage technologies and their deployment. Consequently, the author is adept at discerning loopholes or missed opportunities within the exhibition that may elude the comprehension of ordinary visitors. Thus, the author's impression of the museum and analysis of its exhibition design, even from a visitor's standpoint, may be inherently biased. Relying solely on this method fails to yield a conclusive answer to the question of the cultural value of the brand museum. To comprehensively grasp the impact of brand museums on the communities, additional methodologies such as visitor studies and interviews with the curatorial team are imperative.

Notes

All the pictures in this paper were captured by the author, unless stated otherwise.

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